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Developmental Stages of *Camatkāra* in Sanskrit Poetics

Dr. Sudip Chakravortti¹

Abstract

The treatment of *camatkāra* in Sanskrit poetics collects its essence from word (*śabda*) and meaning (*artha*). Distribution of supernatural curious delight (*adbhutāmodaścamatkārah*) is the purpose. The terms like – non-mundane *ānanda*, *āhlāda*, *vicchitti*, *vaicitrya*, *ramaṇīyatā*, *sadya-para-nirvṛti* etc. synonyms are being used to mean *camatkāra* in the sphere of Indian Poetics. Kuntaka, Ānandavardhana, Viśvanātha, Jagannātha, Kṣemendra, Viśveśvara, Hariprasāda etc. are the supporters of the concept of *camatkāra*. Derivative meaning of *camatkāra* is a matter of enjoyment. Term ‘epiphany’ (a moment of sudden and great revelation or realisation) may be used to represent *camatkāra* in English. *Lāvanya* of a young lady is *camatkāra* of poetry. There is no difference between Ānandavardhana and Kṣemendra. Without *camatkāra*, poetry is useless. So, poets must incorporate the application of *camatkāra* in poetry. Poets must be careful to this end and always search for new and new delightful words to enrich the standard of the poetry. The theory of *camatkāra* is much more significant than *aucitya*. *Camatkāra* was not elaborately discussed by the academicians. On the contrary, *aucitya* gained a huge scope to be consulted in the last few decades. Thus, a very pivotal theory of *camatkāra* was ignored. At the outskirts, it may be assumed that *camatkāra* is only a theory of poetics or literary criticism.

Key Words

Camatkāra, Lokottara-āhlāda, *Lāvanya*, Soul of poetry, Aesthetic pleasure.

The treatment of *camatkāra* in Sanskrit poetics collects its essence from word (*śabda*) and meaning (*artha*). Word and meaning create

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the path of literature (sāhitya). In terms of grammar – the word is vācaka and the meaning is vācya. The Sanskrit rhetoricians do not confine themselves in the sphere of vācya and vācaka only. Slowly but steadily, they nurtured and elaborated the conceptual framework. The meaning and developmental stages of camatkāra in Sanskrit Poetics is attempted here.

Bhāmaha has said that ‘poetry originated with mingling of word and meaning’ (Bhāmaha 4). The germinated seed regarding the definition of poetry in Sanskrit Poetics matured in flowery trees in the eleventh century through the hands of Kuntaka. His notion towards sāhitya bore ripeness and brevity which spoke of non-mundane arrangement of word and meaning. Much more orphean delight may appear when word and meaning do not claim their more or less significance or importance than others (Kuntaka 27).

The spontaneous overflow of inner feelings of a poet is being taken into account to the creation of a poetry. Choice of words and expression of a poet confer the style (rīti) and way (mārga) of poetry. Therefore, Vāmana opined - style is the soul of poetry (Kāvyaśāstrakārasūtravṛtti (Vāmana 11). The arrangement of word and sense are responsible for constituting poetry. But, arrangement of Bhāravi represents the dignified meaning, elegance comes from Daṇḍi and simile-based elegance enchants Kālidasa. The reason behind such differences occurs due to the presence of more or less significance of word and meaning. Vācya and vācaka remain respectful to each other and do not try to overthrow the other. As a result, inherent excellent pretty exudes. Emphasising on it, Kuntaka remarked – true friendship between word and meaning exalts the beauty of poetry and only then it is termed as sāhitya (Kuntaka 11).

In a very lucid way, an appropriate answer to the question related to the purpose of poetry was given by Kuntaka – distribution of supernatural curious delight (adbhutāmōdaścamatkāraḥ) is the purpose. The material elements of practical world transcended into non-mundane by perception (vibhāva), influence (anubhāva) [support (ālabhana) & inspiring (uddīpana)] and transfusing (sañcārī / vyabhicārī) and by excelling it exhales inexplicable

excellence excellent (camatkāra). The unearthly delight (lokottara-āhlada) is the ultimate necessity. Cordial readers of poetry enjoy unearthly delight which comes from none other than excellent. The highest utility of poetry is to render supernatural excellently. Only the cordial readers muse themselves in poetry to be charmed with the flavour of exciting excellence. Kuntaka's antaścamatkāra (spiritual expansion) may be identical with sadyaparanirvṛti (instant poetic pleasure). Even the events of sorrows are amply helpful to rouse ecstasy (Hughes 347). Somehow it may be compared with James Joyce's literary term, "epiphany".

Indian philosophy stands for saccidānanda-svarūpa ātmā. Even Upaniṣadas are accountable for attaining ultimate knowledge of paramātmā. Again, rasa is one kind of thing which is identical with ātmā (soul). Rasa is like the brahma. Ultimate delight regained by rasa (Taittirīyopaniṣat 2-7-2). These immortal speeches of upaniṣad inherently suggest rasa as the soul of poetry. Sanskrit rhetoricians tried to identify the soul of word-meaning based poetry in different ways. Bharata and his followers consider none other than rasa as the soul of poetry. The supporters of alaṅkāra school accepts akaṅkāra as the soul of poetry whereas the exponents of dhvani school directed their concept based on dhvani as the soul of poetry. Moreover, vakrokti is the soul of poetry according to the supporters of vakrokti school. In this way, six or seven schools have emerged in the sphere of Sanskrit Poetics. Hariprasāda (18th century), the composer of Kāvyaśāstra firmly supported camatkāra as the soul of poetry (Hariprasāda 67). Camatkāra was continuously mentioned by most of the eminent Sanskrit rhetoricians on a regular basis. Hariprasāda deeply indulged himself in the matter. Thus, a rarely consulted area (by the present academicians) of Sanskrit Poetics, Camatkāra may claim its position to be a separate school itself.

Camatkāra, the technical term of Sanskrit Poetics primarily arrived from pākāśāstra where it was used to signify charming taste or flavour of prepared food or soft drinks. There are two parts in the onomatopoeic word, camatkāra. After eating a nice food or having an entertaining tea or drinking a tasty juice, we praise in Indic tradition by saying that – it is camatkāra. Again, seeing a

beautiful picture or painting or sculpture people become astonished and express their feeling by using the term, camatkāra. In cricket or tennis or football a great fruitful shot on the part of a player is being welcomed or praised by the term, camatkāra. Whenever we enjoy a lot by observing the catching facts of a drama or cinema or poetry, our feeling is being represented in the form of the term, camatkāra. Thus, in Indian heritage camatkāra plays a great role to fascinate the feeling of inner heart. This is unearthly delight or epiphany.

In the light of Sanskrit Poetics, the pra-pāṇaka-rasa-nyāya may be the actual theory to explain the meaning of camatkāra. Tāmbula, the betel is a widely used matter to taste the charm of betel role. The leaves of betel, lime, areca-nut, anise, coriander, clove, cardamom etc. and other elements are being rolled carefully in betel-role. Then people take an amazing taste of betel-role by chow the same. There different ingredients are present. All of them bear different tastes. But, after a few moments of chowing, one another unforgettable perception of taste is being felt. The camatkāra is more or less the same.

The word camatkāra is derived from camat ($\sqrt{\text{cam}} + \text{śatṛ} = \text{camat}$) & kāra ($\sqrt{\text{kr}} + \text{aṅ} / \text{ghaṅ}$). In upapada-tatpuruṣa the vighraha-vākya is – camantaṁ karoti yaḥ saḥ. Etymologically, cam stands for to sip / drink (Bhaṭṭi 368). But, in practical terms it refers to an inexplicable taste or flavour. The kāra means a performer of any kind of doing or activity or work. So, camatkāra is a matter of enjoyment.

The dictionary meanings of camatkāra are likely – admiration, astonishment, show, spectacle, surprise, uncommon, unusual, ecstasy, exciting excellent, high poetical composition, poetical charm, that which constitutes the essence of poetry (Paṇḍitarāja 147), unearthly delight, etc. The relation with knowledge was ignored in these meanings. Therefore, no exact English term is available to denote camatkāra in a single word to express its relation with knowledge (brahma / ātmā) which comes from poetry. Therefore, the term ‘epiphany’ (a moment of sudden and great revelation or realisation) may be used to represent camatkāra in English.

The terms like – non-mundane ānanda, āhlāda, vicchitti,

vaicitrya, ramaṇīyatā, sadya-para-nirvṛti etc. synonyms are being used to mean camatkāra in the sphere of Indian Poetics. Generally, we use the word camatkāra to express a sense which exceeds the edging of ecstasy. Spontaneous overflow of underlined emotions in the form of exciting excellence is nothing other than camatkāra which comes from poetry. Only the saḥṛdaya² - readers / spectators - are the apt persons to fill their heart with camatkāra.

Poetic matter becomes blended with previously existing emotions in subconscious and unconscious feelings which gains inspiration to be spontaneously overflowed. But we become unable to trace any native personality or colour with the real objective of the practical world around us. It is the transcendental camatkāra which is again alaukika. Therefore, non-mundane excellent or epiphany (alaukika camatkāra) represents a sense like a special aesthetic assertiveness of the mind which is being shaped by the intermingling of the general artistic condition and stimulated sentiment of psychologically motivated developments like –

1. special mental activity to enjoy the whole thing,
2. corporeal expression of delight &
3. inexplicable aesthetic pleasure in the inner heart.

Kṣemendra told– i) except lāvaṇya (comeliness) even any fully faultless beauty of a young lady cannot attract the heart of any youth. ii) The gold becomes sparkling only with the ray of gems. iii) Poetry cannot be placed in first class without camatkāra though it is well-knitted with word, meaning, rhetoric etc (Kṣemendra 76). Here influence of Ānandavardhana is totally visible in respect of camatkāra which is really identical with pratīyamānārtha (dhvani in form of suggested sense) which is expressed only with the help of lāvaṇya (Ānandavardhana 49). It is evident that lāvaṇya of a young lady is camatkāra of poetry. There is no difference between Ānandavardhana and Kṣemendra. Thus, pratīyamānārtha is rasa-dhvani and that is camatkāra of Kṣemendra.

To deal with the definition of poetry, Daṇḍī said – the body of the

2 Yeṣāṃ kāvyānuśīlanabhyāsaśāt viśadībhūte manomukure varṇanīya-tanmayībhavanayogyatā / ta eva hṛdaya-saṃvādabhāja-saḥṛdayāḥ / Dhvanyāloka-locana (by Abhinavagupta)

poetry is the words which express distinguished desired delightful meaning (iṣṭārtha) (Daṇḍin 4). Desired delightful meaning does not mean – your child has taken birth (putra-ste jātaḥ), I must give you a lot of money (dhnām te dāsyāmi). But it significantly reveals unearthly delightful meaning. The mundane profit and loss are not associated with poetry related delightful meaning. In prabhā-ṭikā of Kāvyaadarśa the meaning if iṣṭārtha has been explained in this way – iṣṭārtha is camatkāra based description and camatkāra is unearthly delightful meaning (lokottarāhlāda). The term, camatkāra was in existence even in the time of Daṇḍī.

Though Kuntaka is not being claimed as the exponent of camatkāra, his vakrokti-jīvita abounds in the use of camatkāra irrespective of prelude, utility of poetry, kāvya-mārga etc. Kṣemendra arrived just a few days after Kuntaka. Therefore, the regular use of camatkāra by Kuntaka may impel him to deal with camatkāra with special interest. Aim of poetry is to reflect the varieties of non-mundane camatkāra (Kuntaka 2). By following the same trend, Kuntaka again emphasised camatkāra in his utility of poetry to disseminate the same (Kuntaka 5). Even Mammaṭa accepts this kind of camatkāra as prime among all utilities and says it gives inexplicable knowledge like delight (Mammaṭa 8). Kuntaka also placed camatkāra in the highest position among all utilities. He directly tried to say that poets must create a creation which can arouse camatkāra.

In Āryāsaptaśatī, the poet Govardhana announced that the cream of poetry is camatkāra (Govardhana 3). He expostulated the poets who ignored camatkāra. Kṣemendra also said the same speech, except camatkāra there will be no poet or no poetry: na hi camatkāra-virahitasya kaveḥ kavītvam kāvyasya vā kāvyatvam (Kavikaṇṭhābharaṇa, before verse – 3/2).

During the 14th century AD, Viśvanātha-kavirāja said – the soul of poetry is rasa (Viśvanātha 8). According to him rasa is celestial, undivided, brother-like of Brahma etc. Apart from these adjectives, he firmly recalled camatkāra as the cream or soul of rasa (Viśvanātha 22). To say this, was influenced by Dharmadattasūrī (Viśvanātha 23). Due to the presence of camatkāra, each and every rasa generates

wonderment (vismaya). This wonderment is the sthāyībhāva to stimulate adbhuta-rasa. The root of every rasa is entrenched or sowed in presence of adbhuta-rasa. The definition of camatkāra of Viśvanātha-kavirāja is the state of wonderment (vismaya) which spreads in a profound heart or mind (23). On the basis of wonderment, Viśvanātha-kavirāja accepted vātsalya-rasa as tenth rasa. The acute presence of camatkāra is the only reason for which Viśvanātha-kavirāja considered this vātsalya-rasa (Viśvanātha 89). Only camatkāra is the cream and prime element of any rasa. About 400 years later, famous English poet and critic of the Romantic Period, William Wordsworth gave a quite similar definition of poetry - spontaneous overflow of powerful feelings: it takes its origin from emotion recollected in tranquillity (Wordsworth Preface, 1) - which also longed for wonderment that is nothing other than camatkāra.

The Vaiṣṇava rhetoricians also aware of camatkāra. In Bhaktirasāmṛrasindhu of Rūpagosvāmī, we get different views regarding camatkāra which are likely – a. greatest passionate ecstasy (Hughes 348), “Rati is the cause of all kinds of bliss” (Hughes 275), “an astonishing taste of intense bliss” (Hughes 347), best astonishing bliss (Hughes 157), In Gauḍīya-kaṇṭha-hāra it is seen that – “There are other ingredients, beginning with complete despondency and jubilation. Altogether there are thirty-three varieties and when these combine the mellow becomes very wonderful” (Mahāyogī 9/25). Sanātan(a) Gosvāmī considers camatkāra as unfathomable or wonderful (Gosvāmī 346). Kavikarṇapura also accepts rasa as camatkārakāri and delightful (Kavi Karṇapura 129).

Poetry is an amazing co-operative combination of word and meaning. By following the same trend, the 14th century rhetorician, Viśveśvara’s utmost declaration is – word and meaning must be amalgamated with camatkāra (Mohan 3.). The saḥṛdaya (viduṣa) (Mohan 2) feels inexplicable delight through camatkāra. He also mentioned seven reasons towards the appearance of camatkāra. These are – guṇa, rīti, rasa, vṛtti, pāka, śayyā and alamkṛti (Mohan 2).

He proceeded further by classifying poetry in three categories (camatkāri, camatkāritara & camatkāritama) based on camatkāra

(Mohan 73). Here, the influence of dhvani theory can never be denied. All the śabda and artha based citra or adhama-kāvya in terms of Mammaṭa or only rhetoric-plus poetry are included herein camatkāri. All the guṇibhūta-vyaṅgya based or madhyama-kāvya in terms of Mammaṭa or only asphuṭa-pratīyamānārtha-plus are included herein camatkāritara. And the prime rasa or vyaṅgya based or uttama-kāvya in terms of Mammaṭa or sphuṭa-pratīyamānārtha-plus or dhvani-kāvya poetry are included herein camatkāritama. The author of camatkāra-candrikā was well aware of the prime poetic theories like rasa, dhvani, alaṅkāra etc. which are responsible to beautify poetry. The cautiously included those in camatkāra.

Thus, camatkāra bears a widest meaning to the theory of aesthetic realisation of poetics irrespective of all kinds of poetry throughout the world. This bears a scope of proper cultivation which is yet to be cared for by the scholars. Hope the present researcher will look into the matter in due course with the passage of time and in the very near future. Just an introduction to its development is given herein.

Jagannātha in his Rasaṅgādhara incorporates camatkāra during developed definition of poetry (Paṇḍitarāja 4). Camatkāra exhales inexplicable excellence excellent which gives unearthly delight (lokottara-āhlada) and being enjoyed by the cordial readers (sahṛdaya) of poetry. Only the beautification is accountable for stimulating camatkāra (Paṇḍitarāja 13). The presence of camatkāra and its importance in poetry inspires him to classify poetry like – uttamottama (camatkāritama), uttama (camatkāritara), madhyama and adhama (last two are - camatkāri).

A non-famous rhetorician, Hariprasāda in his Kāvyaśloka strongly refuted recognized theories like rīti, dhvani, rasa etc. as the soul of poetry. He established camatkāra as the soul of all sorts of literary creation (Hariprasāda 67). He also accepted camatkāra as unearthly delight (Hariprasāda 68). This unearthly delight is reason to camatkāra and word which excels unearthly delight is certainly a poetry (Hariprasada 68). The utility and reason of poetry is also associated with camatkāra (camatkārātmaka) (Hariprasāda 67). Alaṅkāra, dhvani, rasa etc. are reasons behind camatkāra. He

nevertheless accepted anything else except camatkāra as the prime theory of poetry. A renaissance silently and gradually took place in the field of literary criticism.

In poetry, role of poet (kavi) and cordial reader (shṛdaya) is very much important. Poet is the creator and determining power assigned to the cordial reader. Camatkāra which is really identical with pratīyamānārtha (dhvani in form of suggested sense) which is expressed through the term, lāvaṇya (Ānandavardhana 49) of Ānandavardhana. It is evident that lāvaṇya of a young lady is camatkāra of poetry. There is no difference between Ānandavardhana and Kṣemendra. Except for camatkāra, poetry is useless. So, poets must incorporate the application of camatkāra in poetry. Poets must be careful to this end and always search for new and new delightful words to enrich the standard of the poetry.

Kṣemendra is famous in the field of Sanskrit poetics due to his Aucityavicāracarcā. The life of poetry is aucitya. The same person expressed his standpoint in connection with the reason for poetry in straightway by saying that – ‘cause of camatkāra is aucitya.’ The mischief of camatkāra is the non-application of aucitya or absence of aucitya. Ingredient of camatkāra is aucitya. Therefore, the theory of camatkāra is much more significant than aucitya. Camatkāra was not elaborately discussed by the academicians. On the contrary, aucitya gained a huge scope to be consulted in the last few decades. Thus, a very pivotal theory of camatkāra was ignored.

At the outskirts, it may be assumed that camatkāra is only a theory of poetics or literary criticism. But, the theory of camatkāra is not only restricted within the poetry. It is further applicable to any kind of aesthetic pleasure irrespective of all sorts of artistic activities which are known as sixty-four kalā or skilful activities or outburst of aesthetic creations.

Works Cited

- Anandavardhana. *Dhvanyāloka*. Edited by Paṭṭābhirāma Sāstrī, Varanasi, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series, 1940.
- Bhāmaha. *Kāvya-lamkāra-sūtra [online version]*. Edited by K.P. Keswan, Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan, 2010.
- Bhaṭṭi. *Bhaṭṭikāvya*. Edited by Vasudeva Laxman Shastri Panshikar, Bombay,

- Pāṇḍuraṅga Jāvajī, Nirnay Sagar Press, 1934.
- B. V. Mahāyogī, editor. Śrī-gauḍīya-kaṅṭha-hārā. Rasbehari Lal & Sons, 2005.
- Daṇḍin. *Kāvyaḍarśa*. Edited by Ramakant Pandey, Delhi, Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan, 2010.
- Gosvāmī, Sanātana. Śrī *Bṛhad Bhāgavatāmṛtam*. Translated by Śrīpada B.V. Viṣṇudaivata and Śrīman Tirthapāda Dāsa, vol. 1, New Delhi, Tirthapāda Dāsa, 2017. 3 vols.
- Govardhana. *Āryasaptaśatī: Anantapaṇḍitakṛtayā vyaṅgyārthadīpanāṭikayā sametā*. Edited by Pandit Durgaprasad and Kashinath Parar, Bombay, Tukaram Javaji, Nirnayasagar, 1895.
- Hariprasāda. *Kāvyaḷoka*. Edited by Rama Gupta, Jaipur, Publication Scheme, 1989.
- Hughes, David Bruce. *Sri Bhakti Rasamṛta-sindhu, Part 1*. Lulu Enterprises Incorporated, 2010.
- Kāvī Karnāpura. *Alankāra Kaustubha*. Edited by Sivaprasad Bhattacharya, Rajshahi, Bengal, Varendra Research Society, 1926.
- Kṣemendra. *Kavikaṅṭhābharāṇa*. Edited by Lele Vaman Keshav, Delhi, Motilal Banarsi Dass, 1967.
- Kuntaka. *The Vakroktijivita*. Edited by Sushil Kumar Dey, 3rd ed., Calcutta, Firma K. L. Mukhopdhyay, 1961.
- Mahāyogī, B. V., editor. Śrī-gauḍīya-kaṅṭha-hārā. Rasbehari Lal & Sons, 2005. Śrī *Gauḍīya Kaṅṭhahāra*, <https://gaudiya.redzambala.com/gaudiya-kanthahara/sri-gaudiya-kanthahara-9.html>. Accessed 25 april 2022.
- Mammaṭa. *Kāvyaṇprakāśa*. Edited by Jivānanda Vidyāsāgara, Calcutta, Kalikata Yantra, 1897.
- Mohan, Pandiri Sarasvati. *The chamatkāra chandrika of sri vishveshvara kavi chandra: Critical edition and study*. Delhi, Meherchand Lachhmandas, 1972.
- Paṇḍitarāja, Jagannātha. *Bhāminivilasam*. Khetwadi, hri Venkateswar Press, 1894.
- Paṇḍitarāja, Jagannātha. *Rasagaṅgādhara*. Edited by Durgaprasad, Nirnay Sagar Press, 1888.
- Vāmana. *Kāvyaḷamkārasūtravṛtti*. Edited by Ramkumar Sharma, Jaipur, Hamsa Prakasan, 2010.
- Viśvanātha. *Sahityadarpana (online)*. Delhi, Rashtriya Sanskrit Sansthan, 2010.
- Wordsworth, William. *Lyrical Ballads with Pastoral and Other Poems*. London, R. Taylor & Co, 1805.

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